

Pilot study of medication adherence in pregnancy*

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Abstract

This study aims to assess medication adherence levels and identify the factors associated with it, among pregnant women in the city of Varna, Bulgaria. A pilot, observational, cross-sectional study was conducted among pregnant women at the Ambulatory Medical Centre for Specialised Care “Prof. Dr. Dimitar Stamatov”, Varna, Bulgaria. Medication adherence was assessed using the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8). The study period was from 15th July 2025 until 15th October 2025. Overall, medication adherence was moderate, with a mean score of 5.92 (SD = 1.62), among the 50 pregnant women who participated in the study (mean age = 31.96; SD = 6.48). No significant associations were observed between adherence and age ($r = 0.044$, $p = 0.760$), educational level ($t(48) = 0.445$, $p = 0.658$), or trimester of pregnancy ($t(48) = 0.901$, $p = 0.372$). Adherence levels did not vary significantly across parity, although a slight, non-significant trend toward higher adherence was observed among multiparous women. Research on medication adherence during pregnancy is still limited, emphasizing the importance of further investigation to better understand adherence behaviours and their determinants in this vulnerable population.

Keywords

associated factors, pregnant women, medication use

Introduction

Pregnancy is a crucial phase in a woman's life, characterized by numerous physiological and hormonal changes that can impact both maternal and fetal health. During this period, a significant proportion of women experience pregnancy-related diseases or preexisting conditions that may necessitate pharmacotherapeutic intervention (Daw et al. 2011; Mitchell et al. 2011). Hypertensive disorders such as hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP) affect around 5–10% of pregnancies

worldwide, contributing significantly to maternal and perinatal morbidity. (Ratnam et al. 2024). Concurrently, gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is the most common medical complication of pregnancy, affecting about 1 in 7 pregnancies globally (Eades et al. 2024). The administration of medications during pregnancy involves complex decision-making, requiring careful evaluation of therapeutic benefits for the mother against potential risks to fetal health. Consequently, healthcare professionals must carefully assess the necessity of each medication and closely monitor both the pregnant woman and the fetus

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throughout treatment. This approach should optimize maternal health while minimizing potential risks to fetal development, ultimately ensuring the best possible outcomes for both mother and child (Palmsten et al. 2015). Moreover, pregnant women should be advised and encouraged to follow healthcare professionals' recommendations regarding medication use closely and to report any drug-related issues they experience. Understanding and promoting behaviours towards medication use is essential to ensure both maternal and fetal health during pregnancy. This highlights the importance of medication adherence (MA), a concept defined by the World Health Organization that reflects the extent to which a patient follows the recommended dosage regimen for taking medications, following a diet, and/or making lifestyle changes (WHO 2003). Emerging data describe non-adherence as a "silent epidemic" contributing to an estimated 21–37% of preventable adverse drug events (Nordeng et al. 2010). A 2019 narrative review confirmed that low medication adherence during pregnancy is widespread (Ceulemans et al. 2019).

A recent study examining women's attitudes toward medication use during pregnancy and breastfeeding found that many perceive medication use in early or late pregnancy as 'possibly dangerous' or 'harmful' (Wolgast et al. 2019). Poor adherence to medications during pregnancy is common and is associated with increased risks of complications, mortality, and significant economic and logistical burden on public health systems due to poor maternal and newborn outcomes (Matsui 2012). Despite this, the level of MA among pregnant women remains poorly understood. Suboptimal adherence to medication poses a serious challenge to perinatal outcomes (Mukona et al. 2018). Furthermore, pregnant women are more reluctant to use medicines and tend to overestimate their teratogenic risk. This risk perception varies depending on the type of medicinal product, level of health literacy, education level, and occupation (Ceulemans et al. 2019). Considering that MA in pregnant women is crucial, as it correlates with improved outcomes for both the mother and the infant (Galappatthy et al. 2018; Hauspurg et al. 2018), it is important to assess and improve current adherence levels. Given these premises, this study investigated therapeutic adherence in a sample of pregnant Bulgarian women, exploring the role of socio-demographic variables (educational level, age, parity, and trimester of pregnancy) and clinical characteristics (comorbid conditions, number of medications) in influencing adherence. Understanding the factors that influence MA during pregnancy is essential, as these findings can guide the development of targeted maternal-health strategies and evidence-based interventions aimed at optimizing treatment effectiveness and improving perinatal outcomes.

Objective

This study aims to assess medication adherence levels and identify the factors associated with it among pregnant women in the city of Varna. This major city was selected

as a representative urban setting with well-organized antenatal services, well-established healthcare infrastructure, and a population profile comparable to other Bulgarian urban regions.

Materials and methods

Study design and participants

We conducted a pilot, observational, cross-sectional study among pregnant patients who followed up their pregnancy at the Ambulatory Medical Centre for Specialised Care "Prof. Dr. Dimitar Stamatov", Varna, Bulgaria. The study period was from 15th July 2025 until 15th October 2025. Structured questionnaire interviews were conducted during their regular antenatal visits with the assistance of medical professionals who had undergone study-specific training, along with a self-administered questionnaire in which participants reported their medication adherence.

Sample size

According to data from the National Statistical Institute of Bulgaria, the number of births in the Varna administrative region in 2024 was 3.647. The initial sample size was calculated to achieve a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error (Δ), using an estimated prevalence (P) of 50% for maximum variability. This calculation resulted in a target sample size of 350 participants, intended to ensure representativeness for the larger study population. However, as this study was designed as a pilot, the final sample size of 50 participants reflects practical constraints encountered during the data collection period. Consequently, this pilot study's results should be considered preliminary, and as a basis for future research with a larger and more representative sample.

Inclusion criteria

Participants were eligible for inclusion if they met all of the following criteria: 1) pregnant women aged 18 years or older; 2) willing to participate and able to provide written informed consent; 3) receiving antenatal follow-up at the Ambulatory Medical Centre for Specialised Care "Prof. Dr. Dimitar Stamatov" in Varna; 4) and able to complete the interview and questionnaire in Bulgarian.

Exclusion criteria

Participants were excluded if they met any of the following criteria: 1) pregnant women were aged under 18 years; 2) declined or were unable to provide informed consent; 3) had cognitive, psychiatric, or language limitations preventing reliable participation; 4) pregnant women referred to the medical centre for high-risk pregnancy follow-up from other regions of Bulgaria, as they were not part of the routinely monitored local patient population.

Data collection procedures

The data collection process consisted of two stages. The first stage involved the extraction of objective clinical information from each pregnant patient's medical record. The following variables were collected: body weight, height, gestational trimester, parity, body mass index (BMI), reported allergies, and comorbid conditions.

The second stage included two components: (1) a structured interview questionnaire conducted with the assistance of medical professionals who had undergone study-specific training, and (2) a self-administered questionnaire in which participants self-reported their medication adherence. The structured interviews were carried out with pregnant women during their regular visits at the antenatal clinic. The interviews were based on a structured questionnaire about patients' demographics, clinical characteristics, and medication use. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions that were arranged in sections. Section A had questions that elicited responses on the demographic data of the pregnant women. Section B comprised questions that elicited responses on the medication use (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Data collection process.

The self-administered questionnaire included a validated instrument: The Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8), used to assess adherence to prescribed antenatal medications.

Medication adherence was tested using the Bulgarian version of the validated eight-item self-report Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) (Krousel-Wood et al. 2009), which includes eight questions with yes or no response options for items 1 through 7 and item 8 has a five-point Likert response scale. Each “no” response is rated as 1, and each “yes” response is rated as 0 except for item 5, in which each “yes” response is rated as 1 and each “no” response is rated as 0. For Item 8, the code (0–4) has to be standardized by dividing the result by 4 to calculate a summated score. Total scores on the MMAS-8 range from 0 to 8, with scores of 8 reflecting high adherence, 7 or 6 reflecting medium adherence, and <6 reflecting low adherence. Permission to use the scale was granted by Philip Morisky, the copyright holder of the instrument (Certificate Number: 1974-5692-3114-1759-0205/01.05.2025).

Statistics

We employed a range of statistical methods to analyze and evaluate relationships within the data of interest. Group comparisons for continuous variables were conducted using independent-samples *t*-tests (for two groups) and one-way ANOVA (for more than two groups). Clinical and demographic variables to identify predictors of medication adherence were explored. Relationships between study variables (medication adherence) were examined using Pearson (for parametric data) correlations. We utilized the SPSS statistical software.

Results

Patients' demographic and clinical characteristics

A total of 50 questionnaires representing 100% of all participants were included for analysis. Table 1 presents the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants. The sample is primarily composed of women aged 30–39 (48%) and 18–29 (42%), followed by those aged 40 and above (10%) ($p = 0.0019$). The sample is dominated by persons with higher education (78%), ($p < 0.0001$). It was

Table 1. Patients' characteristics.

Patients' characteristics	N respondents (%)
Age group	
18–29	21 (42%)
30–39	24 (48%)
>40	5 (10%)
Educational level	
Elementary school	0 (0%)
High school	11 (22%)
Bachelor's degree/ Master's degree	39 (78%)
Trimester of Pregnancy	
First (4–9w.)	0 (0%)
Second (13–27w.)	24 (48%)
Third (28–40w.)	26 (52%)
Parity of the pregnancy	
First pregnancy	24 (48%)
Second pregnancy	16 (32%)
Third pregnancy	5 (10%)
Fourth pregnancy or more	5 (10%)
Comorbidity	
With a coexisting conditions	26 (52%)
Without a coexisting condition	24 (48%)
Type of Medicine Used	
Prescription Medications	41 (82%)
Non-prescription Medications	3 (6%)
Pregnancy supplements	6 (12%)
Herbal products	0 (0%)
Amount of taken medications	
1–2	9 (18%)
3–5	30 (60%)
>5	11 (22%)

estimated that 48% of pregnant patients were in the second trimester, while 52% of all were in the third trimester of pregnancy ($p < 0.00001$). Parity distribution showed that almost half of the participants were primigravida ($n = 24$), followed by second pregnancy ($n = 16$), and higher parity was less common, third pregnancy ($n = 5$) and fourth and above ($n = 5$) ($p < 0.0001$). A majority (48%) of the individuals enrolled in the study have been diagnosed with co-existing disease ($p = 0.78$). Regarding medication use during pregnancy, a significant proportion of patients, 41 (82%), reported taking at least one prescription medication, while 6% of them were taking only over-the-counter medications and 12% were taking only supplements ($p < 0.0001$).

Medication adherence level

In this pilot study, the overall medication adherence measured by the MMAS-8 was moderate with a mean score 5.92 (SD = 1.62) among the 50 pregnant women who participated in the study (Table 2).

Table 2. Mean medication adherence level.

Variable	Mean MMAS	SD	95% CI
MMAS-8 score	5.92	1.62	5.47–6.37

Legend: MMAS-8, Morisky Medication Adherence Scale-8.

Factors associated with adherence level

Pearson's correlation analysis was applied to examine the relationship between age and medication adherence. No significant associations were observed between adherence and age ($r = 0.044$, $p = 0.760$). (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Medication adherence levels by age.

An independent samples t-test showed no significant difference in MMAS-8 adherence scores between women with higher education and those with secondary education ($t(48) = 0.445$, $p = 0.658$). The mean difference between groups was small (0.25 points), indicating that educational level did not influence medication adherence in this sample.

The t-test was conducted to compare medication adherence score (MMAS-8) between patients in second- and

those in third trimester of pregnancy. The analysis showed no statistically significant difference in adherence scores between the second and third trimester of pregnancy ($t(48) = 0.901$, $p = 0.372$, mean difference = 0.41 (95% CI: -0.51 to 1.34) (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Medication adherence score by trimester of pregnancy.

Medication adherence differed slightly across parity groups, although the differences were not statistically significant according to the one-way ANOVA analysis ($F = 0.812$, $p = 0.372$). Women in their first pregnancy demonstrated a mean MMAS-8 score of 6.14 ± 1.50 ($n = 24$), while those in their second pregnancy had a lower mean adherence score of 5.14 ± 1.89 ($n = 16$). Participants in their third pregnancy showed a mean score of 6.30 ± 0.96 ($n = 5$), and the highest adherence was observed among women with four or more pregnancies (7.00 ± 0.71 , $n = 5$) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Medication adherence levels by parity number. Legend: MMAS-8, Morisky medication adherence scale 8-item.

An independent samples t-test showed no significant difference in medication adherence between participants with and without chronic disease ($t(48) = -0.246$, $p = 0.807$). Mean adherence scores were 5.87 ± 1.67 for those without and 5.98 ± 1.60 for those with chronic disease (mean difference -0.11, 95% CI: -1.05 to 0.82). Participants using OTC medications had the lowest adherence (mean 5.08 ± 2.90), while mean adherence was highest among those taking 1–2 medications (mean 6.67 ± 0.41), followed by 3–5 medications (mean 5.87 ± 1.53) and >5 medications (5.45 ± 2.28). Although adherence tended to decline with increasing medication burden, this trend did not reach significance ($F = 1.450$, $p = 0.245$) (Table 3).

Table 3. Analysis of socio-demographic and clinical factors.

Patients' characteristics	Mean MMAS-8	SD MMAS-8	95% CI	p-value	F / t
Age group					
18–29	6.05	1.74	5.24–6.86	0.213	F=1.598
30–39	5.59	1.59	4.73–6.44		
>40	6.95	0.72	6.22–7.68		
Educational level					
High school	6.11	1.34	5.48–6.74	0.658	t=0.445
Bachelor's degree/ Master's degree	5.86	1.70	5.32–6.42		
Trimester of Pregnancy					
First (4–12w.)	0	0		0.372	t=0.901
Second (13–27w.)	6.14	1.40	5.57–6.71		
Third (28–40w.)	5.72	1.80	5.01–6.42		
Parity of the pregnancy					
First pregnancy	6.14	1.50	5.52–6.76	0.081	F=2.393
Second pregnancy	5.14	1.89	4.14–6.14		
Third pregnancy	6.30	0.96	5.19–7.41		
Fourth pregnancy or more	7.00	0.71	6.14–7.86		
Coexisting Conditions					
With	5.87	1.67	5.20–6.54	0.807	t=-0.246
Without	5.98	1.59	5.31–6.65		
Type of Medicine Used					
Prescription Medications	5.83	1.59	5.33–6.33	0.186	F=1.746
OTC (over-the-counter medications)	5.08	2.90	-2.11–12.28		
Pregnancy supplements	6.96	0.64	6.29–7.63		
Number of medications taken					
1–2	6.67	0.41	6.36–6.97	0.245	F=1.450
3–5	5.87	1.53	5.31–6.43		
>5	5.45	2.28	4.01–6.89		

Hence, it can be asserted that there is no statistical basis for asserting differences in adherence levels among the various factors considered. These findings suggest that adherence behaviours in pregnancy may be influenced by factors other than routine demographic or clinical characteristics, such as perceptions of medication safety, risk beliefs, or quality of counselling – elements that will be explored in the large-scale study (Table 3).

Discussion

This pilot study confirms that MA among pregnant women remains suboptimal with overall adherence, measured using the MMAS-8, showing a moderate mean score of 5.92. This finding is consistent with prior research indicating that adherence during pregnancy is often inadequate due to concerns about medication safety, negative beliefs, and fears of fetal harm (Lupattelli et al. 2014; Sontakke et al. 2021). No significant association was found between age and MA ($r = 0.044$, $p = 0.760$), which aligns with earlier research suggesting that age alone is not a strong predictor of medication-taking behaviour in pregnancy (Lupattelli et al. 2014). Nonetheless, older pregnant women appear to show improved adherence according to emerging evidence (Ba et al. 2019; Cordova-Ruiz et al. 2025). The absence of such an association in the present pilot study

may be related to the small sample size or limited age variability. Educational level similarly showed no significant influence on adherence ($t(48) = 0.445$, $p = 0.658$), despite common assumptions that higher education leads to better understanding of treatment recommendations (Sontakke et al. 2021; Carbone et al. 2025).

Adherence also did not significantly differ by parity ($F = 0.812$, $p = 0.372$). Although multiparous women showed slightly higher adherence, the differences were small and not statistically significant. This observation contrasts with previous studies reporting that women with prior births may be more prone to low adherence (Lupattelli et al. 2014; Kamau et al. 2018; Obiekwu et al. 2020).

The absence of statistically significant associations across demographic variables suggests that MA in pregnancy is likely driven by factors beyond standard socio-demographic indicators. Prior research highlights that perceptions of risk, medication safety beliefs, trust in healthcare providers, counselling quality, and patient-provider communication strongly influence adherence in pregnant women (Juch et al. 2016; Undela et al. 2021). These factors were not assessed in this pilot but will be incorporated in the full-scale study to better understand the psychological and behavioral drivers of adherence.

Consistent with findings from broader chronic-disease literature, taking more than two types of medication is associated with lower adherence (Belsti et al. 2025; Putri et

al. 2025). Our pilot study revealed the same trend, with adherence decreasing as the number of medications increased. However, this association did not reach statistical significance, likely due to the limited sample size and reduced statistical power characteristic of pilot studies. Women with comorbidity, taking multiple medications, have a higher risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes such as preterm and caesarean deliveries, which can complicate adherence (Belsti et al. 2025).

Similar challenges to therapy adherence emerge across different socially significant groups of patients. Studies consistently show that adherence in elderly patients with chronic illnesses is determined by factors such as polypharmacy, cognitive limitations, and reduced social support, with more than half of participants in several cohorts demonstrating low or moderate adherence levels (Félix and Henriques 2021; Cardona et al. 2025). In populations with chronic diseases more broadly, adherence rates remain variable and often inadequate, with estimates indicating that up to half of patients fail to take medications as prescribed; this trend intensifies in the presence of multimorbidity, regimen complexity, or low health literacy (Maffoni et al. 2020). These studies align with our findings by underscoring that adherence among socially significant groups remains suboptimal and is influenced by factors that extend beyond basic sociodemographic characteristics. Importantly, they also emphasize the need for tailored, multifactorial interventions that address not only clinical needs but also the emotional and social context of vulnerable patient populations.

Recent pan-European data demonstrate considerable differences in how healthcare professionals approach medication adherence, emphasizing the need for more unified practices and improved training. These observations reinforce the relevance of developing tailored adherence-support strategies, which is particularly important for vulnerable groups such as pregnant women. In the context of our findings, this further highlights the necessity of implementing consistent, evidence-based approaches to promote optimal medication use during pregnancy (Kamusheva et al. 2024). Recent research highlights the importance of addressing medication adherence barriers at different levels, from patient awareness to health system technology and to fostering collaboration between HCPs (Hafez et al. 2024).

Policies that engage multidisciplinary teams and support informed, shared decision-making may also improve adherence outcomes for pregnant women managing chronic or gestational conditions. Medication Use Review (MUR) can be a significant intervention to optimize medicine use and improve health outcomes especially for patients with chronic diseases (Petrova et al. 2023) (Tuula et al. 2024). Findings from other Bulgarian settings also underscore the importance of structured, patient-centred interventions in improving medication adherence (Ivanova et al. 2022) and Bulgarian pharmacists' positive attitude towards digital transformation (Pesheva et al. 2022). Additional insights into medication adherence challenges in Bulgaria come from a national survey among hospital and

community pharmacists, which highlights the broader systemic factors influencing patients' adherence to chronic therapies (Tsvetkova et al. 2021).

The moderate adherence levels observed among pregnant women in this study align with broader patterns reported in Bulgaria, where structural and communication-related barriers may limit optimal medication use. Recent research in the area demonstrated that nearly half of patients with chronic conditions, such as rheumatoid arthritis, do not consult pharmacists, and that pharmacists themselves report insufficient training and limited incentives to provide comprehensive pharmaceutical care services. These gaps in the pharmaceutical care infrastructure may similarly affect pregnant women, who require individualized counselling regarding medication safety. Strengthening pharmacist-led educational and counselling interventions could therefore represent an important strategy for improving adherence during pregnancy (Maruleva et al. 2025).

Strengths and limitations

One potential limitation of the study is the relatively small sample size, with only 50 pregnant patients included. The findings of this study may not be generalizable to other regions in Bulgaria with distinct characteristics, especially in terms of healthcare access. Furthermore, a notable weakness of the study is the limited amount of available research on the topic, which restricts the breadth of comparison and generalization of our findings. Moreover, the heterogeneity in study designs and outcome measures across existing literature further reduces the comparability of the results.

The study relied on self-reported measures of medication adherence, which may be subject to recall bias or social desirability bias. Another constraint arises from the absence of a thorough examination of the factors impacting medication adherence. A longitudinal follow-up study is recommended to assess whether adherence behaviours change over time or in response to educational interventions.

Strengths of the study include the use of various statistical methods to analyze the data and the inclusion of multiple demographic and clinical variables. The study also utilized a standardized medication adherence test, which provides a quantitative measure of adherence. Moreover, the research was conducted at The Ambulatory Medical Centre for Specialised Care "Prof. Dr. Dimitar Stamatov", Varna, which serves patients from across Northeastern Bulgaria, providing outpatient care. This increases the representativeness of the sample.

Conclusion

There is a notable lack of studies investigating medication adherence in pregnant populations in Bulgaria, highlighting the need for more comprehensive research on adherence-related determinants within the local antenatal care

context. This study addresses this gap as the first to focus specifically on medication adherence among Bulgarian pregnant patients. The findings identify key clinical and demographic factors associated with adherence during pregnancy and emphasize the importance of patient ed-

ucation, targeted counselling, and systematic adherence monitoring in prenatal care. Future research involving larger populations is warranted to validate these results and inform the development of interventions aimed at optimizing medication use during pregnancy.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki on ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects and Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data. Ethics approval was obtained by the Medical University Varna Ethics Committee (Ethics Approval Number 17/03.07.2025).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

Tanya Kazakova and Anna Todorova contributed to the conception and design of the study. Material preparation, data collection, and analysis were performed by Tanya Kazakova. Tanya Kazakova wrote the first draft of the manuscript, and all the authors commented on previous versions. All authors read and approved the final manuscript. The authors would like to acknowledge Professor Maria Kamusheva for her valuable contribution to the critical revision of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.